

Book(s) of Esther

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Jewish Traditions, Text, Scripture, Jewish Court Tales, Early Jewish Literature, Religious Holidays

Esther is part of the Writings (ketuvim) in the Hebrew Bible. It is a court drama that, in two of its earliest editions, details an etiology for Purim, a Jewish holiday which is celebrated on 14 Adar (usually sometime in February or March in the Gregorian calendar). In addition to the Hebrew text, there are also two early Greek versions, the Alpha Text (AT) and Old Greek (OG), which were written during the Second Temple Period. Both the AT and OG have later Greek additions, which are additional chapters that elaborate on the story. It is likely that the additions came from the same source, since they have so much in common. The Old Greek version of Esther and its additions are found in the Septuagint (LXX). Most 2nd Temple scholars agree that Esther is a fictional tale. That being said, while nearly every character is fictionalized, and many of the inner workings of the Achaemenid court are fictionalized or exaggerated for the sake of hyperbole, Esther still can tell us about some of the cultural tensions present at the time of its composition. The story also provides us with a possible setting for the invention of the holiday of Purim: the Jewish Diaspora. Esther is unique in that it is the only book in the Hebrew Bible that does not mention the Jewish god. The Greek versions of Esther resolve this by inserting God's name into the text. The Greek additions to Esther even flesh out some of the ritual practices in the Hebrew text to include prayer. The Hebrew and Greek versions of Esther follow the same basic outline. The setting is the court of Susa, the capital of the Achaemenid Empire. The story begins with an extravagant banquet hosted by the king of Persia. The king becomes drunk, and asks that his queen be brought before the court. The queen refuses, and is removed from her position as queen and banished from the court. After this, the king must find a new queen—so all the young virgins of the land are brought to the court, one of whom is Esther, a Jewish girl. Esther had been living in Susa with Mordecai, her cousin and caretaker. Mordecai also plays a prominent role in the story due to his political rivalries. After entering the king's palace, Esther wins the king's favor and is soon made queen. There are political tensions between her cousin, Mordecai, and Haman, who is second in command of the entire kingdom. Haman creates a plot to kill all Jews in the kingdom. Mordecai informs Esther of the plot, and she tells the king at a banquet that she hosts for Haman and him. Haman is executed, and the Jews are given free rein to fight back against their adversaries. In all versions but the Greek Alpha Text, the holiday of Purim is established by an official decree to commemorate Esther saving her people.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 70 CE

Region: Western Asia & North Africa

Region tags: Levant, Greece, Egypt, Iran, Southern Iraq

The Hellenistic empire throughout the time of 2nd Temple Judaism, 333 BCE - 70 CE.

I want a map showing Iran, Iraq, the Levant, Egypt, and Greece. Please mark Alexandria in Egypt, Susa in Iran (modern-day Shush), and Babylon in Iraq.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Source and Summary

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Esther (Masoretic Text)
- Source 2: Esther (Septuagint)
- Source 3: Esther (Alpha Text)

Notes: See also Josephus: The Jewish Antiquities 11.6.1-13 184-296.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The earliest manuscript we have of the Hebrew text of Esther is from the Leningrad Codex, which dates to 1008 CE and was produced in Cairo by the Masoretes. This text was written on parchment paper, and the Masoretes added vowels to aid pronunciation. The Dead Sea Scrolls, which were produced during the 2nd Temple period, were written on parchment and papyrus, but do not contain the versions of Esther. However, we can assume that the original manuscripts of the versions of Esther would have been produced using similar materials.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Specify type of paper

– Specify: papyrus; parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

—Other [specify]: Texts were copied by scribal communities. Any corrections or changes were likely decided upon before text was reinscribed.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: Elite Religious Specialists

↳ Tomb
— No

↳ Cemetery
— No

↳ Temple
— Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the canon was in flux during the 2nd Temple period, we cannot say for certain whether or not manuscripts of Esther would have been housed at any of the Temples during this time.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: Elite Religious Specialists

↳ Shrine
— No

↳ Altar
— No

↳ Devotional marker
— Field doesn't know

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

Notes: Christian churches did not exist at the time of composition. However, Esther did become incorporated into Christian traditions.

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While no textual evidence has been uncovered from any of the 2nd Temple synagogues, iconography depicting Esther is found at later synagogues such as the Byzantine-era Dura Europos Synagogue. It is possible that early manuscripts of Esther were housed at synagogues for the purpose of being read aloud on the Festival of Purim, although there is not much evidence that Purim was a widely celebrated festival during the 2nd Temple period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Field doesn't know

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's possible that at least one of the versions of Esther could have been stored in the Library of Alexandria, and feasible that the versions of Esther would have been archived somewhere in the 2nd Temple period. However, it's difficult to say when our earliest surviving manuscript dates to 1008 CE, which is almost a millennium after the 2nd Temple period had ended.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to the colophon at the end of the Septuagint (LXX), its translation and production appear to have been funded by the priestly elite in Jerusalem. It is highly likely that the priestly elite (likely those in the Diaspora) funded the production of the Hebrew manuscript and Alpha Text as well, since this was the class of people that wrote much of the Hebrew Bible, although the lack of 2nd Temple Esther manuscripts makes it difficult to say for certain.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: It depends which community you ask. For example, there are no copies of Esther found among the Dead Sea Scrolls, suggesting that the Qumran community did not celebrate Purim. The canon was in flux during this time, so we cannot use terms like "official scripture" when discussing biblical texts from the 2nd Temple period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Hebrew and Greek were both spoken by laypeople. While Hebrew started to die out as a spoken language during the Persian Period (559-331 BCE), there still were pockets of Hebrew speakers present in Palestine during the 2nd Temple period, especially in Yehud/Judah. For communities that did not have many Hebrew speakers, the text would be read aloud at the synagogue and translated into Aramaic - this act of translation is the origin of the Aramaic Targumim.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 37 BCE

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ On the reciter?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The festival of Purim involves the text of Esther being read aloud or recited. A later rabbinic tradition (Megillah 7b:7) suggests that the festival involved drinking alcohol.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Once per year on 14 or 15 Adar

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Purim may have been synchronous with the Zoroastrian new year. More research needs to be done in this area.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Megillah 7b:7 discusses drinking wine during Purim. This is a later rabbinic interpretation, and may not necessarily have been practiced during the 2nd Temple period.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The Hebrew Bible and Septuagint both enjoin practitioners to feast and send portions of food to their neighbors.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

Notes: The Greek Alpha Text does not directly address Purim.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: Esther is currently part of the "Writings" (ketuvim) and could be considered a festival text, but these seem to be categories imposed on it after the 2nd Temple period.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Notes: Esther and Mordecai are connected to the Benjaminites, one of the first tribes of Israel. This makes them connected by blood to Saul, the first king of Israel.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

- ↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?
 - No
- ↳ Marriage?
 - No
- ↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?
 - No
- ↳ Divorce?
 - No
- ↳ Warfare?
 - No
- ↳ Funerary services?
 - No
- ↳ Trade/commerce?
 - No
- ↳ Festivals?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Frequency of festivals?
 - Specify: Establishes Purim as occurring once per year.
 - ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?
 - All members
 - ↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?
 - number: N/A
 - ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?
 - Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?
– No

↳ Pilgrimages?
– No

↳ Feasting?
– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?
– No

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?
– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?
– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?
– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?
– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?
– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: The Greek versions of Esther attest to the Jewish god's existence, but the divine is not a direct actor/agent.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: One thing that the versions of Esther discuss is how to survive under foreign powers.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

Notes: The Greek additions discuss Esther's moral dilemma with her failure to remain ritually pure, but ultimately she is successful in spite of it.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: The versions of Esther depict fasting as an appropriate ritual mourning response, but do not mandate it.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 8766

Notes: Festival occurs once per lunar calendar year.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 8766

Notes: Festival occurs once per lunar calendar year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– Yes

Notes: Discussed in Greek Additions to LXX and Alpha Text

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

Notes: Discussed in Greek versions

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Lineage is an in-group marker discussed in Esther

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: A diaspora group

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Most likely the elite priestly classes

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Giving of food portions on festival day

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The majority of rabbinic educational centers would have arisen after the destruction of the 2nd Temple in Jerusalem. Synagogues that practiced Purim would have taught the text.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

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